

<i>Celleporella hyalina</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	0.1%	0.1%		0.1%	3.3%	96.5%
<i>Celleporina caliciformis</i> (Lamouroux, 1816)					3.0%	97.0%
<i>Chorizopora brongniartii</i> (Audouin, 1826)					3.4%	96.6%
<i>Conopeum reticulum</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)						100%
<i>Crassimarginatella tensa</i> (Norman, 1903)						100%
<i>Cribrilina</i> (<i>Cribrilina</i>) <i>cryptooecium</i> (Norman, 1903)		3.0%			11.9%	85.1%
<i>Crisia eburnea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		30.8%				69.2%
<i>Crisidia cornuta</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	5.0%	5.0%			15.0%	75.0%
<i>Crisiella producta</i> (Smitt, 1865)						100%
<i>Diplosolen obelium</i> (Johnston, 1838)						100%
<i>Disporella hispida</i> (Fleming, 1828)					12.5%	87.5%
<i>Einhornia arctica</i> (Borg, 1931)						100%
<i>Einhornia</i> sp.						100%
<i>Electra pilosa</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	0.2%	0.8%	0.6%	1.0%	12.4%	85.0%
<i>Eucratea loricata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			3.3%			96.7%
<i>Flustra foliacea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	1.8%					98.2%
<i>Flustrellidra hispida</i> (Fabricius, 1780)					25.5%	74.5%
<i>Juxtacribrilina annulata</i> (Fabricius, 1780)		2.4%			24.4%	73.2%
<i>Membranipora membranacea</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)				1.8%		98.2%
<i>Membraniporella nitida</i> (Johnston, 1838)					89.8%	10.2%
<i>Microporella ciliata</i> (Pallas, 1766)					46.4%	53.6%
<i>Notoplites</i> sp.	100%					

<i>Diphasia attenuata</i> (Hincks, 1866)								100%
<i>Diphasia fallax</i> (Johnston, 1847)		20.0%						80.0%
<i>Dynamena pumila</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	1.3%	3.5%	0.4%	0.4%	1.7%		62.9%	29.7%
<i>Filellum serpens</i> (Hassall, 1848)			0.4%		0.9%	0.4%		98.2%
<i>Grammaria abietina</i> (Sars, 1851)							33.3%	66.7%
<i>Grammaria</i> or <i>Lafoea</i>								100%
<i>Hydrallmania falcata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	0.03%		0.02%				1.3%	98.6%
<i>Lafoea dumosa</i> (Fleming, 1820)							10.5%	89.5%
<i>Lafoea</i> sp.	50.0%		50.0%					
<i>Laomedea angulata</i> Hincks, 1861								100%
<i>Modeeria rotunda</i> (Quoy & Gaimard, 1827)								100%
<i>Obelia dichotoma</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)				0.3%	14.2%	39.9%	1.1%	44.5%
<i>Obelia dichotoma</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) or <i>Obelia longissima</i> (Pallas, 1766)			100%					
<i>Obelia longissima</i> (Pallas, 1766)				1.3%	84.7%	1.3%	2.7%	10.0%
<i>Opercularella lacerata</i> (Johnston, 1847)			1.7%	0.8%		60.0%	8.3%	29.2%
<i>Orthopyxis integra</i> (MacGillivray, 1842)					0.9%	3.5%	3.9%	91.7%
<i>Phialella quadrata</i> (Forbes, 1848) or <i>Eutonina indicans</i> (Romanes, 1876)					34.4%	59.4%	6.3%	
<i>Sertularella rugosa</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			3.0%	3.0%	9.1%	3.0%		81.8%
<i>Sertularella</i> sp. 1: <i>Sertularella clausa</i>			50.0%					50.0%
<i>Sertularella</i> sp. 2: <i>Sertularella gayi</i>								100%
<i>Sertularella</i> sp. 3: <i>Sertularella polyzonias</i>	9.1%				18.2%			72.7%

<i>Sertularia</i> sp. 1: <i>Sertularia cupressina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) or <i>Sertularia argentea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			1.4%				12.2%	86.4%
<i>Sertularia</i> sp. 2: <i>Sertularia fabricii</i> (Levinsen, 1893)								100%
<i>Sertularia</i> sp. 3: <i>Sertularia similis</i> (Clark, 1877) or <i>Thuiaria articulata</i> (Pallas, 1766)	100%							
<i>Symplectoscyphus tricuspidatus</i> (Alder, 1856)	0.2%		0.3%		4.8%	7.8%	13.3%	73.6%
<i>Tamarisca tamarisca</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)			50.0%					50.0%
<i>Urticina felina</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)								100%
Mollusca								
<i>Heteranomia squamula</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)							9.3%	90.7%
<i>Hiatella arctica</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)								100%
<i>Mytilus edulis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	7.8%	1.4%	6.1%	0.3%	0.3%	1.0%	1.4%	81.6%
<i>Pododesmus patelliformis</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)								100%
<i>Turtonia minuta</i> (Fabricius, 1780)	1.2%	65.4%					3.7%	29.6%
